

Driving Industry 5.0 Success: How Theory Meets Practice in Europe's Industrial Evolution

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Abstract—As industries move beyond the digital focus of Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0 emerges as a new paradigm prioritizing human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience in production processes. However, a significant gap remains in translating these theoretical advancements into practical implementation. This paper addresses this gap by combining a Systematic Literature Review of 879 articles with a two-round Delphi study involving 14 experts from diverse European sectors, including Consumer Goods, Life Sciences, and Heavy Industry. The resulting framework, organized around strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers, synthesizes theoretical insights with sector-specific perspectives. Through the Delphi process, 32 hypotheses were refined to 24 consensus-based findings, creating a robust, evidence-backed foundation. This research offers actionable insights for industry and academia, bridging theoretical and practical dimensions of Industry 5.0.

Keywords—Industry 5.0, Delphi Study, European Companies

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry 5.0 (I5.0) shifts the focus from the technology-driven paradigm of Industry 4.0 to human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience. This new industrial approach not only addresses global challenges like climate change and resource scarcity but also enhances competitiveness through human-focused, sustainable practices [1]. Within Europe, where industries are under increasing pressure to fulfill both societal and regulatory demands, I5.0 is identified as a strategic priority, reflecting an alignment with broader social and environmental goals [2]. Despite theoretical advancements, a comprehensive understanding of I5.0 remains lacking, as theory and industrial practice often diverge in focus. While current research predominantly emphasizes enabling technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and human-machine collaboration, it falls short of providing an integrated framework for practical application across diverse industrial sectors [3, 4]. This disparity highlights the need for industry-academia collaboration to develop a shared understanding of I5.0, bridging theory and practice while considering diverse operational priorities across sectors. Addressing this gap is essential for industries to fully realize the potential of I5.0. Therefore, this paper seeks to answer the following research question:

How can industry and academia collaboratively conceptualize the foundational dimensions of Industry 5.0 to foster a shared understanding that bridges theoretical frameworks and practical implementation across diverse European sectors?

II. RELATION TO EXISTING THEORIES AND WORK

I5.0 builds upon the foundations of Industry 4.0 but marks a pivotal shift in industrial paradigms. However, this transition is not sequential but complementary. Companies can build on digital foundations while already integrating human-centric and sustainable practices [5]. While Industry 4.0 prioritized automation, digital connectivity, and efficiency through AI and Internet of Things (IoT), it largely neglected critical dimensions such as human well-being, environmental sustainability, and systemic resilience [6]. These omissions have raised concerns about their long-term viability, particularly regarding socio-ecological impacts. In response, I5.0 embeds human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience at the core of industrial development, aiming to create a more balanced and adaptable system [1]. Current literature offers diverse perspectives on I5.0. Some studies focus on enabling technologies, implementation challenges [7], and application potentials [8], while others explore strategic frameworks and theoretical foundations [9, 10]. Despite these contributions, research remains fragmented, offering limited insights into the effective operationalization of these principles across industries. Moreover, the accelerated adoption of I5.0 – spurred by crises such as COVID-19, market volatility, and geopolitical instability – has underscored the urgent need for resilient and future-proof industrial frameworks [11, 12].

This study addresses these gaps by integrating theoretical insights and empirical evidence through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and a Delphi study. By framing I5.0 around strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers, it offers a practical framework that bridges theoretical concepts with real-world application. This approach advances the discourse on transitioning beyond Industry 4.0, emphasizing not just efficiency but also long-term social and environmental sustainability.

III. RESEARCH APPROACH

A. Research Objective

This study aims to address the gap between the theoretical foundations of I5.0 and its practical applications across diverse European industrial sectors by fostering a collaborative framework that unites academic and industry perspectives. To achieve this, the research proceeds in two phases. First, a SLR following the PRISMA method is conducted to design and populate an initial structure with theoretical insights, specifically focusing on the key dimensions of I5.0: human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience. This preliminary framework is organized around strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers, forming a foundation grounded from the theoretical perspective.

Building on the initial structure defined by the SLR, the next phase involves aligning and refining these theoretical insights with practical, industry-specific perspectives. This was achieved through a Delphi study, engaging 14 experts from 14 different European countries, each representing diverse sectors such as Consumer Goods, Life Sciences, and Heavy Industry. This collaborative phase aims to validate and adapt the preliminary framework, ensuring that the strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers identified are fully aligned to real-world industrial contexts.

By synthesizing academic and industry perspectives, the Delphi study provides a comprehensive, consensus-based structured pathway for aligning theoretical dimensions of I5.0 with industry-specific needs, to bridge the gap between theoretical frameworks and practical applications.

B. Research Methodology

This study employs a dual-method approach, combining an SLR to establish the theoretical foundations of I5.0 and a Delphi study to incorporate practical insights from industry experts. This approach ensures a holistic understanding of I5.0 that incorporates both academic and industrial perspectives.

1) Systematic Literature Review

The SLR serves as the foundational phase, undertaken to derive an initial core structure – comprising strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers – essential for fostering a shared understanding of I5.0. This structure is then populated with theoretical insights drawn from a thorough analysis of relevant literature, setting a robust foundation for further empirical validation. To ensure methodological rigor, transparency, and replicability, the SLR followed the PRISMA methodology, a widely adopted and endorsed SLR approach. It comprises evidence-based guidelines that support authors in conducting and reporting their review [13]. This phase was designed to both establish an organizing framework – comprising strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers – and populate this structure with a robust theoretical foundation.

Following the methodology, the review process involved several steps: identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and final inclusion (see Fig. 1). The SLR utilized three academic databases – SCOPUS, Science Direct, and Web of Science – selected for their extensive coverage of peer-reviewed literature. An initial set of 879 sources was filtered through multi-stage criteria, ultimately refining the dataset to 61 key studies. These were then analysed for thematic contributions to the framework. By mapping recurring

Fig. 1. Systematic literature review following PRISMA methodology (own visualization).

concepts, a core structure of strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers was identified, embedding them with theoretical insights that reflect the evolving academic discourse on I5.0. This framework provided a preliminary foundation, setting the stage for empirical refinement in the Delphi study.

2) Delphi Study

Building upon the theoretical foundations established through the SLR, a Delphi study was conducted to elicit and refine practical industry perspectives from across Europe. This method is characterized by the use of questionnaires, expert participation, anonymity of responses, aggregation of group results, and iterative rounds [13] and therefore well-suited to facilitate a systematic assessment of expert opinions, and to align them with I5.0's theoretical constructs. Targeting a range of sectors, including Consumer Goods, Life Sciences, and Heavy Industry, the primary aim of the Delphi study was to elucidate how organizations interpret and operationalize I5.0 principles, with a particular focus on addressing real-world challenges and identifying key technological enablers.

The Delphi study engaged 14 experts from distinct European countries, and data collection was structured into two rounds. These experts were drawn from the industrial partners of the PROSPECTS 5.0 initiative, ensuring a sectorally and geographically diverse panel (see Table I). Their selection followed a purposive sampling approach, chosen to ensure participants had direct, context-specific expertise [14] in implementing I5.0 principles within their organizations. This method suits the exploratory nature of the study, prioritizing depth, relevance, and practical insight over representativeness. To mitigate common limitations of purposive sampling, such as sectoral or regional bias, the diversity of the consortium ensured a balanced mix of industrial and national perspectives. Moreover, the Delphi method's iterative, anonymized process supported a more neutral aggregation of expert opinions.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF DELPHI PANEL CHARACTERISTICS (OWN VISUALIZATION)

Countries represented	14 (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Türkiye)
Industrial sectors	Consumer Goods (28,6%), Life Sciences (35,7%), Heavy Industry (35,7%)

In the first Delphi round, conducted from June 17 to July 13, 2024, experts responded to 12 open-ended questions focusing on strategic objectives, triggers, and enablers for I5.0. In addition, the experts had the opportunity to share other relevant insights not covered by the questions. As leaders in driving technological advancements and sustainability in their companies, they contributed insights that led to the derivation of 32 preliminary hypotheses, addressing sector-specific challenges and cross-sector themes such as technological advancement, workforce development, and sustainability integration.

The second round of the Delphi study, conducted from July 15 to August 12, 2024, utilized closed-ended questions derived from the initial 32 hypotheses to rigorously assess expert consensus. A 5-point Likert scale facilitated quantitative evaluation, with consensus measured through descriptive statistics, focusing on median values and interquartile ranges (IQR) [15, 16]. Hypotheses that achieved a median score above 3 and an IQR below 1, in accordance with [16], were deemed to reflect strong agreement, leading to the retention of 24 validated hypotheses (see Table II). These accepted hypotheses provided the foundation for refining strategic objectives, further articulated through additional supporting dimensions, as well as the integration of complementary triggers and enablers specific to industry contexts. As detailed in Fig. 2, this process aligns theoretical foundations with sector-specific insights, creating a comprehensive approach that facilitates the practical implementation of I5.0 across diverse European industrial sectors.

This structured and statistically validated approach ensured that only hypotheses with substantial expert support were included in the final framework. The results, as summarized in Fig. 3, present a robust, evidence-based model that bridges theoretical and practical perspectives on I5.0 implementation.

IV. FINDINGS

This section presents the findings from two complementary approaches: Theoretical foundations from the SLR and Industry Perspective from the Delphi study, which are then combined in the Integrated Findings. As shown in Fig. 2, the SLR established a core framework for I5.0 with 3 strategic objectives, 6 triggers, and 5 enablers based on academic literature, forming a theoretical foundation for I5.0 principles.

Building on this structure, the Delphi study incorporated industry-specific perspectives from 14 European experts, enhancing the framework with 6 additional dimensions to deepen the understanding of the three core strategic objectives, along with 4 supplementary triggers and 7 additional enablers. This process aligned theoretical elements with practical sectoral needs, enhancing the framework with actionable insights tailored to real-world challenges. The integrated findings establish a comprehensive framework (see Fig. 3) that fosters a shared understanding between academia and industry, addressing the research question by aligning the foundational dimensions of I5.0 across diverse European sectors. This shared understanding is crucial for enabling the targeted implementation of I5.0's core pillars of human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience. By literature and practical applications, the framework provides a collaborative

Fig. 2. Overview of integrated findings for I5.0 (own visualization).

foundation that empowers academia and industry to jointly conceptualize and strategically implement I5.0 principles.

A. Theoretical Foundation

The SLR provides an in-depth analysis of the theoretical drivers and enablers of I5.0. These insights highlight the key elements that shape this emerging industrial paradigm, including technological advancements, human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience.

1) Strategic Objectives

The transition to I5.0 is driven by external triggers, alongside internal enablers. Key strategic objectives include fostering resilience, sustainability, and human-centricity [17, 18]. Foundational values are consistently highlighted in the literature as critical for I5.0 adoption [19].

2) Triggers of I5.0

- Acute Crises:** The COVID-19 pandemic and similar large-scale disruptions have revealed the limitations of traditional industrial systems in responding to sudden shocks. These crises expose the fragility of global supply chains and underscore the need for resilient and adaptive industrial frameworks [20, 11]. I5.0 responds to these crises by emphasizing the development of agile systems capable of withstanding unforeseen challenges [21, 22].
- Ethical Challenges and Social Responsibilities:** Growing societal demands for ethical business practices and corporate social responsibility require industries to consider the social and environmental impacts of their operations. I5.0 aligns with these societal expectations by promoting a balanced approach that integrates economic performance with social and environmental well-being [9, 23].
- Market Changes:** Consumer demand for personalization and customization is reshaping the industrial landscape. This shift toward more individualized products requires flexible production systems that can adapt quickly to market changes. I5.0's human-centric approach places the customer at the center of the production process,

necessitating advanced technologies to accommodate these demands [22, 18].

- **Planetary Boundaries:** Environmental sustainability is becoming an imperative for industries operating within the limits of planetary boundaries. The need to reduce environmental impacts and operate within ecological constraints has pushed industries to adopt more sustainable practices. I5.0 emphasizes ecological responsibility, driving industries to innovate toward greener production methods [24].
- **Political Volatility and Crises:** In an increasingly interconnected global economy, political instability and regulatory shifts can disrupt industrial operations. The ability to adapt to these changes is essential for maintaining operational continuity. I5.0 encourages industries to develop strategic flexibility, allowing them to remain resilient in the face of political crises [25, 26].
- **Talent Recruitment and Retention:** As industries become more technologically advanced, the need for skilled labor increases. Attracting and retaining talent has become a critical challenge, particularly as younger generations seek more meaningful work environments that emphasize well-being and autonomy. I5.0's focus on human-centricity directly addresses these workforce dynamics by creating environments that prioritize continuous learning and development [10, 27].

3) Enablers of I5.0

- **Anchoring I5.0 Objectives:** For industries to effectively transition to I5.0, its core principles, human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability, must be deeply embedded within corporate strategies. Companies that align their business models with these objectives are better equipped to navigate the complexities of modern industrial challenges. This requires the integration of real-time data analytics, advanced decision-making tools, and agile business models to ensure adaptability and resilience [25, 11].
- **Deploying Technologies:** The integration of technologies such as AI, IoT, and collaborative robots is essential for realizing I5.0's human-machine collaboration model. These technologies enhance operational efficiency, flexibility, and customization, enabling industries to meet the growing demand for personalized products and services. Recent frameworks, such as preference-based optimization models [28] and digital twin systems [29] offer concrete strategies to operationalize human-robot collaboration by enabling real-time simulation of joint tasks and dynamically adapting robotic behavior based on human input. Crucially, I5.0 redefines the role of technology, moving beyond process automation to actively augment and enhance human capabilities [8].
- **Leveraging Interdisciplinary Synergies:** I5.0 thrives on the intersection of multiple disciplines, from engineering and information technology to social sciences and business management. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, industries can develop more comprehensive solutions to complex challenges. This collaborative approach not only drives innovation but also ensures that diverse perspectives are integrated into decision-making processes [10].

- **Upskilling and Enablement:** As industries embrace more complex technologies, the workforce must be equipped with the necessary skills to operate in an increasingly digital environment. Upskilling programs that focus on both technical proficiencies – such as AI, robotics, and data analytics – and soft skills, including critical thinking and creativity, are essential for maintaining a competitive workforce. Continuous learning ensures that employees can adapt to evolving industrial needs, fostering a more engaged and capable workforce [30].

Operationalizing Technologies: Beyond the adaptation of new technologies, industries must establish the necessary frameworks for an ethical and sustainable use of technology. This includes developing robust governance structures, ensuring data security, and adhering to ethical standards in AI and machine learning. By creating the infrastructure to support responsible technology deployment, companies can ensure that they remain competitive while mitigating potential risks [31, 10].

B. Industry Perspective

The Delphi study provides a rigorous examination of the practical application of I5.0 principles across various sectors. Informed by expert insights from industry professionals, this section explores the tangible challenges, technological enablers, and strategic approaches that organizations are currently employing to facilitate the transition to I5.0. It highlights how sector-specific realities shape the adoption of human-centric, sustainable, and resilient practices, offering a comprehensive view of the operational adjustments required to implement this emerging industrial paradigm effectively. In particular, the findings reveal meaningful sector-specific distinctions, such as differing emphasis on regulatory alignment, financial constraints, or technological infrastructure, which underline the need for tailored implementation strategies instead of a one-size-fits-all approach. These nuanced differences not only inform practice but also extend prior theoretical work on I5.0 enablers [9, 6] by empirically grounding abstract concepts like human-centricity and resilience within concrete organizational contexts.

1) Strategic Objectives Human-Centricity

- **Development of Technical Skills:** The hypothesis that "AI integration in I5.0 will optimize production processes and enable the development of customer-specific products within the next decade" (Median = 4.5, IQR = 1) received broad support, underscoring its role in advancing industry-specific innovation. In the Consumer Goods sector, AI within I5.0 aims to enhance product customization and speed in response to shifting consumer preferences. For Life Sciences, AI-driven precision manufacturing will enable the production of highly specialized health and pharmaceutical products, aligning with the sector's stringent safety and regulatory needs. In Heavy Industry, AI is positioned to transform operational efficiency by automating large-scale, complex processes and facilitating predictive maintenance, which are critical for sustainable and resilient industrial operations. This consensus reinforces the need for AI-related technical skills across sectors, highlighting I5.0's emphasis on adaptive, customer-oriented, and human-centric production models.

- **Development of Soft Skills:** The importance of soft skills such as communication, problem-solving, and adaptability was also recognized as a key strategic objective. The hypothesis that "ignoring the development of soft skills will leave the workforce unprepared for I5.0 challenges" (Median = 4, IQR = 0.75) was widely accepted, indicating strong support for balancing technical training with soft skill development. These skills are seen as essential for enabling effective collaboration in increasingly automated environments and for fostering human-centric innovation. Soft skills' development is a critical objective for I5.0, with widespread recognition of the need to cultivate these skills to complement technological advancements and maintain human-centric innovation.
- **Redefining the Roles of Humans in Industrial Revolutions:** The Delphi study emphasized that leveraging human creativity, decision-making, and problem-solving abilities is crucial for I5.0 to avoid stagnation and drive innovation (Consolidated Median = 4, IQR = 0.75). Additionally, prioritizing skills diversification through partnerships with educational institutions was widely supported as essential for preparing a resilient workforce (Consolidated Median = 4.5, IQR = 1). Together, these insights highlight that redefining human roles by emphasizing creativity and fostering industry-academia collaboration will be vital for achieving sustained industrial progress and adaptability in I5.0. Given AI's growing capabilities in creative tasks, human creativity must focus on meta-level activities, such as framing problems, applying ethical judgment, and integrating cross-disciplinary insights. Rather than competing with AI, humans add value by contextualizing, challenging assumptions, and focusing on societal goals.

2) Strategic Objectives Resilience

- **Integrating Autonomous Systems:** Autonomous systems were strongly endorsed as a key component of industrial resilience. The hypothesis that "integrating autonomous systems is crucial for I5.0 to effectively respond to dynamic market conditions" (Median = 4, IQR = 0) highlighted broad agreement across sectors. Autonomous systems were recognized for enhancing operational flexibility and enabling rapid adaptation to change market environments, a crucial element for ensuring business continuity and long-term resilience. The integration of autonomous systems is essential for building resilience in I5.0, particularly in enhancing operational flexibility and enabling industries to adapt swiftly to market changes.
- **Promoting Visibility in Leadership Roles:** The hypothesis that "failing to foster visibility in leadership roles will undermine employee engagement, whereas promoting these elements will enhance the strategic contribution of human skills" (Median = 4, IQR = 0.75) underscored the importance of leadership visibility in fostering a resilient workforce. While this was strongly supported across sectors, Consumer Goods showed some resistance, possibly due to a stronger focus on automation. Nevertheless, Life Sciences and Heavy Industry emphasized leadership visibility as key to aligning human skills with strategic goals, which directly contributes to organizational resilience. Leadership visibility is a critical element of resilience in I5.0,

fostering employee engagement and aligning human skills with long-term strategic objectives.

3) Strategic Objectives Sustainability

- **Integration of Sustainable Practices and Methods:** The Delphi study identified strong support for integrating sustainable practices as a strategic objective, with two central hypotheses. The first suggests that "I5.0 strategies combining innovative technologies and energy efficiency will drive economic growth and competitiveness in European industries over the next decade" (Median = 4, IQR = 0.75), emphasizing energy efficiency as a competitive asset. The second hypothesis posits that "integrating sustainable practices, including energy-efficient technologies and circular economy principles, is crucial for achieving long-term environmental and economic benefits in I5.0" (Median = 4, IQR = 1). Life Sciences and Heavy Industry experts strongly endorsed this, while Consumer Goods cited financial and practical challenges. These findings indicate that, while sustainability is a priority, its feasibility differs, depending on economic and operational conditions. Additionally, sustainable practices often progress through incremental improvements rather than systemic change. High investment costs, slow technological adoption, and regulatory inconsistencies remain key barriers.

4) Triggers of I5.0

- **Digital Transformation:** Digital transformation emerged as a widely accepted trigger, validating its crucial role in driving operational efficiency across sectors. The hypothesis, that "digital transformation is not just a trend but a revolution accelerating the adoption of sustainable practices in I5.0" was overall accepted (Median = 4, IQR = 1), reflecting a consensus, that I5.0's success relies heavily on an adaptive, tech-enabled workforce across sectors.
- **Global Competition:** The hypothesis that "global competition is a major economic driver of the transition to I5.0" received strong support, highlighting the critical role of external pressures in accelerating technological adoption (Median = 4, IQR = 1). Sectors such as Life Sciences and Heavy Industry emphasized the urgency of adapting to competitive pressures to maintain relevance, with global competition pushing them toward advanced technological integration. In contrast, the Consumer Goods sector placed a stronger focus on internal factors like cost control and operational efficiency, indicating that while global competition is a catalyst, its immediate impact varies by sector. These findings underscore that global competition is a key driver of I5.0 adoption, though its influence varies by sector and is strongest in industries under high external pressure.
- **Holistic Approach:** The importance of a holistic approach to I5.0 was strongly supported, particularly by Life Sciences, which emphasized the need to integrate sustainability and human-centric innovation. The hypothesis that "a holistic approach, incorporating sustainability and human-centric innovation, is essential for I5.0's evolution" (Median = 4.5, IQR = 1) highlighted a broad consensus that successful implementation depends on aligning technological progress with sustainability and human needs. This goes beyond theoretical models by emphasizing the practical

integration of these elements into operational strategies, especially in sectors like Life Sciences, where such factors are already deeply embedded. A holistic, human-centric approach is key to I5.0's success, with strong sectoral support for integrating sustainability and innovation, particularly within Life Sciences.

- **Technological Advancements:** The Delphi study strongly affirmed that advancements in AI, robotics, and IoT are pivotal drivers of operational efficiency within I5.0, with broad consensus across all sectors (Median = 5, IQR = 1). These technologies are seen as essential for streamlining processes, enabling automation, and improving real-time data visibility, crucial for enhancing productivity and adaptability. Although the specific adoption of certain technologies may vary by sector, the overall significance of technology in achieving I5.0 objectives remains undisputed. These advancements collectively underscore the shift towards a more efficient, connected, and responsive industrial landscape.

5) Enablers of I5.0

- **Additive Manufacturing:** The hypothesis that “additive manufacturing is a key technology revolutionizing production processes in I5.0, increasing production flexibility” received widespread support (Median = 4, IQR = 1) underscoring its role in enhancing operational adaptability and innovation. Additive manufacturing is recognized for its ability to enable customized, on-demand production, thus reducing material waste and promoting resource efficiency. By allowing for more agile and scalable manufacturing processes, this technology aligns with I5.0's goals of fostering flexible, human-centric, and sustainable industrial environments. This strong backing suggests that additive manufacturing will be essential in supporting I5.0's objectives by driving advancements in production flexibility and meeting diverse, evolving market demands.
- **Advanced Data Analytics:** The hypothesis that failing to leverage advanced data analytics will leave organizations lagging behind received unanimous support across sectors (Median = 5, IQR = 1). Advanced data analytics is recognized as essential for driving innovation and operational excellence by enabling real-time decision-making, optimizing efficiency, and enhancing resilience. By harnessing data-driven insights, companies can better anticipate market shifts, streamline production processes, and effectively integrate sustainability initiatives. This consensus underscores that data analytics is not only a key enabler for I5.0 but a crucial differentiator for firms aiming to maintain a competitive edge in a rapidly evolving industrial landscape.
- **Policy and Regulation:** The hypothesis that “proactive government policies are essential catalysts for the successful implementation of I5.0 technologies” was supported, with strong consensus on the transformative role of regulatory frameworks (Median = 4, IQR = 0.75). In sectors like Life Sciences, proactive policies were seen as pivotal in driving sustainability and technological integration, highlighting government intervention as a necessary facilitator of I5.0 goals. However, the Consumer Goods sector exhibited scepticism, emphasizing the importance of aligning policies with market realities to ensure industry-wide adoption without

disrupting operational autonomy. These findings suggest that while effective regulatory frameworks can accelerate I5.0 adoption, tailored alignment with sector-specific needs is crucial for maximizing their catalytic impact.

- **Artificial Intelligence:** AI was widely recognized for its role in optimizing production and enabling customization, with high support across sectors (Median = 4.5, IQR = 1). AI enhances operational efficiency by automating routine tasks, allowing human workers to focus on creative problem-solving. However, variability in adoption was noted in Consumer Goods, where concerns about costs and implementation challenges surfaced. Conversely, Life Sciences saw AI as critical to both operational optimization and sustainability. AI is a core enabler across sectors for enhancing operational efficiency and enabling human creativity, though challenges in cost and implementation may slow its immediate adoption in certain industries.
- **Collaboration:** The hypothesis that “collaboration between industry, government, and academia fosters innovation” was broadly accepted (Median = 5, IQR = 1), yet scepticism persisted in Heavy Industry regarding the efficiency of such partnerships (IQR = 2). The alignment of regulatory frameworks with industry needs emerged as a significant factor influencing the effectiveness of collaboration. While most sectors acknowledge collaboration's role in driving innovation, its implementation remains uneven, with Consumer Goods favouring market-driven approaches over government-led interventions. Collaboration is viewed as a vital enabler for innovation, though industry scepticism about regulatory efficiency may hinder its impact, particularly in sectors like heavy industry.
 - **IoT:** The “integration of IoT” was consistently identified as essential for achieving seamless connectivity and improving operational visibility (Median = 5, IQR = 1). Its role in enabling real-time data exchange and supporting advanced analytics was widely accepted, with industries recognizing IoT as foundational for implementing I5.0 strategies. Life Sciences highlighted IoT's potential for improving resource management and sustainability, while Heavy Industry emphasized its importance in facilitating operational adjustments. IoT is a universally accepted enabler, crucial for enabling real-time data integration and decision-making.
 - **Skills Diversification:** The hypothesis that “I5.0's evolution in job roles and skills will necessitate stronger collaboration between industry and educational institutions” received widespread support (Consolidated Median = 4, IQR = 1). As I5.0 reshapes workforce demands, sectors like Consumer Goods (Median = 4.5, IQR = 1.25) particularly emphasized the need for diversified skills to meet evolving consumer expectations and adapt to rapid technological change. Life Sciences (Median = 4, IQR = 0) and Heavy Industry (Median = 4, IQR = 1) similarly recognized the value of industry-academia partnerships in fostering specialized technical and soft skills, which are critical for operational resilience and innovation. These findings underscore that as I5.0 redefines job roles, structured collaboration with educational institutions will be essential to ensure a workforce capable of meeting new industry standards and supporting sustainable growth.

TABLE II. DELPHI STUDY ANALYSIS (MEDIAN, M; INTERQUARTILE RANGE, IQR; HYPOTHESIS ACCEPTANCE, A; HYPOTHESIS REJECTION, R; CONSUMER GOODS, C1; LIFE SCIENCE, C2; HEAVY INDUSTRY, C3)
(OWN VISUALIZATION)

Open questions Round 1		Statements Round 2 [respective industry dimension in the framework for accepted hypotheses]	Consolidated		C1		C2		C3		
			M	IQR	A/R	M	IQR	M	IO	M	IO
Strategic Objectives	What should be the primary objectives of I5.0 for companies, besides aspects of profit generation?	I5.0 initiatives that prioritize both technological advancement and human-centric innovation will increase adoption rates of the concept and foster a positive perception of the concept [Strategic objective: Human centrality].	4	1	A	4	2	5	1	4	0
		Resilient business models that support talent development are essential for achieving long-term success in I5.0 initiatives [Strategic objective: Resilience].	4	1	A	4	0,75	4	1	4	1
		The implementation of sustainable practices, including the use of renewable energy sources and optimized waste management, is crucial for I5.0 success [Strategic objective: Sustainability].	5	1	A	4,5	1,75	5	0	4	1
	How can I5.0 contribute to the long-term economic growth and competitiveness of European industries?	I5.0 strategies that integrate innovative technologies with emphasizing energy efficiency will increase economic growth and enhance competitiveness in European industries within the next decade [Integration of sustainable practices and methods].	4	0,75	A	3,5	1,25	5	0	4	0
		The integration of AI in I5.0 will optimize production processes and facilitate the development of customer-specific products within the next decade [Development of technical skills].	4,5	1	A	5	0,25	4	0	5	1
		Efforts in upskilling employees and fostering human-robot collaboration in I5.0 will increase industry resilience [Strategic objective: Resilience].	4	0,75	A	4	0,25	5	1	4	0
	How can European industries integrate sustainable practices into their operations during the transition to I5.0?	The integration of sustainable practices, including energy-efficient technologies and circular economy principles, is essential for European industries to achieve long-term environmental and economic benefits within I5.0 [Integration of sustainable practices and methods].	4	1	A	4	2,25	5	1	4	0
		European industries that fail to adopt energy-efficient technologies and embrace circular economy principles within I5.0 will fall behind.	4	1,75	R	3	2,25	4	0	4	1
	What specific sustainability goals are most important for your company to achieve in the next five years?	Optimizing raw material utilization will significantly boost companies' success in sustainability.	4	1,5	R	5	0,25	4	0	3	1
		Developing digital skills among employees will position companies better for sustainability success [Strategic objective: Sustainability].	5	1	A	4,5	1	5	0	4	1
		I5.0 initiatives that fail to leverage human creativity, decision-making, and problem-solving abilities will stagnate, whereas prioritizing these aspects will redefine the role of humans in industrial innovation and drive significant advancements [Redefining roles of humans in industrial revolutions].	4	0,75	A	4	2	4	1	4	0
	How should I5.0 redefine the role of humans within the industrial environment?	Without a strong emphasis on human-machine collaboration, I5.0 will fall short of its potential.	4	1,75	R	4	0,75	4	2	4	1
Prioritizing skills diversification through strong collaboration between industry and educational institutions will result in a well-equipped workforce for I5.0 [Redefining roles of humans in industrial revolutions].		4,5	1	A	4,5	1	5	1	4	1	
Impact on Jobs and Skills: What are the potential impacts of I5.0 on job roles, skills, and workforce development?	Ignoring the development of soft skills will leave the workforce unprepared for the challenges and opportunities of I5.0 [Development of soft skills].	4	0,75	A	4,5	1,5	4	0	4	0	
	Fostering human-robot collaboration boosts I5.0's ability to manage disruptions.	4	1,5	R	5	0,5	4	1	4	0	
How can I5.0 help industries better prepare for and respond to disruptions (e.g., economic, environmental, technological)?	Prioritizing process standardization will significantly enhance I5.0's preparedness while improving process efficiency.	4	1,5	R	4,5	1	3	1	4	0	
	Integrating autonomous systems is crucial for I5.0 to effectively respond to dynamic market conditions [Integrating autonomous systems].	4	0	A	4	0,5	4	0	4	0	
In what ways can I5.0 technologies support business continuity and adaptability?	Failing to foster visibility in leadership roles will undermine employee engagement, whereas promoting these elements will significantly enhance the strategic contribution of human skills [Promoting visibility in leadership roles].	4	0,75	A	3,5	1,5	4	0	4	1	
	Technological advancements such as AI, robotics, and IoT are crucial drivers in facilitating operational efficiency in I5.0 [Technological advancements].	5	1	A	5	0,25	5	1	5	1	
Triggers	What are the primary technological, economic, ecological, and social triggers driving the transition to I5.0?	Global competition is a significant economic factor influencing the transition to I5.0 [Global competition].	4	1	A	4,5	1,25	4	1	4	1
		The promotion of circular economy practices significantly influences the transition to I5.0, enhancing sustainability.	4	2	R	3,5	1,75	4	1	4	2
	What roles do global trends and challenges (e.g., climate change, digital transformation) play in accelerating I5.0?	A holistic approach that addresses global challenges, incorporating human centrality at the forefront of innovation, is essential for I5.0 to successfully evolve and adapt [Holistic approach].	4,5	1	A	4,5	1	5	1	4	1
		Adoption of advanced automation techniques by companies is driven by customer demands.	4	1,75	R	3,5	3	4	1	4	2
Enablers	What are the key technologies and innovations that will enable the transition to I5.0 in your opinion?	Digital transformation is not just a trend but a revolution that is radically accelerating the adoption of sustainable practices in I5.0, making it an indispensable driver for achieving environmental goals and operational efficiency [Digital transformation].	4	1	A	3,5	1,5	5	1	4	1
		Additive manufacturing is a key technology that revolutionizes production processes in I5.0, increasing production flexibility [Additive manufacturing].	4	1	A	4	0,5	4	0	3	1
		The integration of IoT is crucial for the seamless connectivity and real-time data exchange in I5.0, enhancing operational visibility [Internet of Things].	5	1	A	4,5	1	5	0	4	1
	How can collaboration between industry, government, and academia facilitate the development and implementation of I5.0?	I5.0 initiatives that fail to leverage advanced data analytics will be left behind, as these technologies will propel adopters to a significant boost in innovation and operational excellence [Advanced data analytics].	5	1	A	5	0,5	4	0	5	0
		The integration of AI is not just beneficial, but essential for accelerating the adoption and effectiveness of I5.0 in practice [Artificial Intelligence].	4,5	1	A	4,5	1,5	4	1	5	1
		Effective collaboration between industry, government, and academia significantly enhances innovation, supporting the growth of I5.0 [Collaboration].	5	1	A	5	0,25	4	1	5	2
	Practical industry-related education will be the linchpin in enhancing collaboration between industry, government, and academia.	4	1,75	R	4	0,25	3	2	4	2	
	Proactive government policies will be the catalyst for transforming and successfully implementing I5.0 technologies [Policy and regulation].	4	0,75	A	3	2,25	4	1	4	0	
	The evolution of job roles and skills diversification brought by I5.0 will mandate increased collaboration between industry and educational institutions [Skills diversification].	4	1	A	4,5	1,25	4	0	4	1	

Fig. 3. Framework of integrated findings (own visualization).

C. Integrated Findings

The integrated findings, illustrated in Fig. 3, reveal three core dimensions of I5.0, human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability, that align theoretical and practical perspectives. Academic literature emphasizes these pillars, identifying human-machine collaboration, adaptable autonomous systems, and circular economy practices as central. The Delphi study supports this, with experts stressing the need for balanced skill development, particularly through interdisciplinary collaborations with educational institutions, to prepare a resilient workforce. Resilience emerges as crucial, where integrating autonomous systems and visible leadership roles strengthens organizational adaptability. Sustainability is highlighted across sectors, though Consumer Goods note barriers such as cost and regulatory challenges, while Life Sciences and Heavy Industry prioritize energy-efficient technologies and circular economy models. Triggers and enablers, positioned around the core pillars, further enhance the practical relevance of these dimensions. This framework provides a structured approach for advancing I5.0 by bridging theoretical insights with real-world applications across diverse sectors.

V. CONCLUSION

This study effectively bridges theoretical foundations with practical insights into I5.0, establishing human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability as core pillars requiring nuanced, sector-specific strategies. A central finding is the substantial variability in the adoption of transformative technologies, such as AI and IoT, shaped by distinct financial and operational priorities across sectors. Notably, while Life Sciences demonstrates advanced integration of autonomous systems and circular economy models, Consumer Goods encounters significant financial and regulatory obstacles, highlighting the need for tailored rather than generalized approaches. This insight suggests that the successful implementation of I5.0 depends not merely on technological availability but on each sector's unique economic and structural context. The study also

uncovers stark differences in sustainability integration capacity, with Life Sciences positioned for circular models while sectors like Consumer Goods and Heavy Industry face pronounced barriers. These findings underscore the necessity of adaptive regulatory frameworks that support sector-specific needs without hindering growth, pointing to a critical insight: regulatory strategies must be responsive to diverse industry requirements to ensure sustainable, sector-wide transformations.

Another significant contribution is the identification of workforce development as essential to human-machine collaboration in I5.0. Findings emphasize the importance of both technical and soft skills, best achieved through interdisciplinary partnerships with educational institutions, which calls for a new, integrated model that aligns technical proficiencies with human-centered competencies. While the combined use of SLR and Delphi study methods provides a robust, consensus-based foundation for I5.0, the distinct methodological approaches reveal limitations that highlight the need for actionable strategies in the next stage of research. The SLR offers a comprehensive theoretical framework but may lack the granularity required to address sector-specific practicalities essential for effective implementation. Conversely, the Delphi study's consensus-driven approach can simplify sectoral complexities, potentially overlooking nuanced operational distinctions by prioritizing broad agreement over fine-grained insights. To unlock I5.0's full potential, future research should move beyond foundational analysis to develop targeted strategies that address the unique demands and operational realities of diverse industrial sectors, ensuring adaptable and effective I5.0 transitions.

This study makes a significant contribution to I5.0 research by developing a comprehensive, understanding of I5.0 that bridges theoretical foundations with practical application across European industries. Synthesizing findings from an SLR and Delphi study, the research identifies strategic objectives as human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability as core pillars of I5.0, organized around triggers, and enablers. Despite the

strategic objectives being established in prior literature, this study contributes novel insights by detailing, how these are interpreted and prioritized differently across industrial sectors. The results of the Delphi study offer an expanded understanding of I5.0's practical realization. Importantly, the study highlights that the adoption of transformative technologies, such as AI and IoT, requires customization to fit each sector's unique financial, operational, and regulatory landscape. For instance, the Life Sciences sector demonstrates readiness for advanced technologies and circular economy practices, while the Consumer Goods sector faces significant economic and regulatory constraints, underscoring the need for tailored rather than one-size-fits-all approaches.

A central insight from the study is the importance of workforce development that balances both technical and soft skills. Through interdisciplinary training and collaboration with educational institutions, such development is crucial for enabling effective human-machine collaboration. These findings carry practical implications for policymakers and industry leaders, suggesting that regulatory frameworks must be adaptable and sector-sensitive to facilitate sustainable I5.0 transitions.

While this framework offers a solid foundation, certain methodological limitations should be noted. The SLR may lack the granularity needed for addressing nuanced sector-specific requirements, and the consensus-driven Delphi study could mask sectoral variations by focusing on broad agreement. Future research should, therefore, emphasize refining sector-specific strategies to enhance the framework's practical relevance and impact.

In conclusion, this study provides critical groundwork for a collaborative, sector-sensitive approach to I5.0 that merges academic insight with industry practice, integrating technology, workforce development, and regulatory adaptation. By cultivating a cohesive understanding of I5.0's foundational dimensions, this framework represents a significant advancement toward practical adaptation and implementation across diverse sectors. Such an approach has the potential to drive balanced and resilient growth, positioning I5.0 as a catalyst for sustainable, human-centered transformation within Europe's industrial landscape.

MATCH & CONTRIBUTION

This contribution aligns well with the theme of the ICE IEEE 2025 conference on "AI-driven Industrial Transformation: Digital Leadership in Technology, Engineering, Innovation & Entrepreneurship", specifically with the "Industry 5.0" track. The paper presents a structured framework for implementing Industry 5.0, developed through a SLR and a Delphi study involving experts from three European industrial sectors. It examines how technologies are translated into sector-specific strategies and addresses the operational and organizational challenges that influence their implementation. By integrating theoretical and practical perspectives, the study provides actionable insights for aligning human-centric, resilient, and sustainable innovation with real-world industrial needs. This contribution addresses the conference's focus on leveraging data-driven and context-sensitive approaches to guide effective technological adoption and industrial transformation, making it a relevant

and valuable addition to the conference proceedings. Additionally, this paper also aligns with the broader objectives of IEEE TEMS by providing a practical framework and addressing the management of emerging technology.

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